

Solubility of Benzoic and Salicylic Acids in Mixtures of Organic Solvents.

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It seems that very little work seems to have been undertaken with a view to study the behaviour of three types of mixtures namely (i) two comparatively non-polar, (ii) polar and non-polar, and (iii) two polar solvents, on the solubility of organic acids.

With a view to study the three types of mixtures on the solubility of benzoic and salicylic acids, the present work was undertaken. The same method described by the authors (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 131), was followed for the estimation of the solubilities of the organic acids.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

In Figs. 1-6 are plotted the results of the solubility of benzoic acid in mixtures containing varying amounts of organic solvents. It can be seen from Fig. 1 where the solubility of the acid in mixtures of two non-polar liquids is plotted, that the curves are almost straight lines.

FIG. 1.

Curves 1—3 refer to mixtures of benzene with toluene, xylene and hexane respectively.

FIG. 2.

Curves 1—3 refer to mixtures of CHCl_3 with benzene, toluene and xylene respectively.

FIG. 3.

Curves 1—3 refer to mixtures of acetone with benzene, xylene and toluene respectively

FIG. 4.

Curves 1—4 refer to mixture of benzene with MeOH, EtOH, n-PrOH and n-BuOH respectively.

This linear relation is due to the fact that when two non-associated liquids are mixed, very small volume and temperature changes occur (cf. Walker and Henderson, *Trans. Roy. Soc. Canada*, 1902, 105, 8). These results are also in agreement with the conclusion arrived at by Padoa and Mattencci, (*Atti. R. Accad. Lincei* 1914, 23, 590) from their work on the surface tension of a mixture of benzene and toluene. The nature of the curves obtained when salicylic acid was used as a solute was the same as that in the case of benzoic acid.

Chloroform which is slightly polar seems to act in an abnormal manner as can be seen from Fig. 2. The solubility of the acid in its presence is less than what it should be according to the simple mixture rule. It is probable that it makes a very loose complex with the solute and the effect of the addition of an aromatic hydrocarbon is to inhibit this formation.

When acetone which is polar in nature is used as a component of the mixture with the aromatic hydrocarbons, the curves are convex to the concentration axis of the mixture. The presence of acetone increases the solvent power of the hydrocarbons on account of its polar character. This accounts for the increased solubility of the acid. The same was also found in the case of salicylic acid.

The solubilities of benzoic acid in mixtures of benzene as one component and different alcohols as other components are plotted in Fig. 4. In mixtures of the above type, the non-polarity of benzene will be greatly affected by the presence of strongly polar alcohols and this, in turn, will greatly increase the solvent action of the aromatic hydrocarbon. This increase is in accordance with the solvent power of alcohols on benzoic acid. Methyl alcohol which has been found to have the greatest solvent action on the acid increases the solubility of the acid to approximately 1.7 times that calculated according to the ideal mixture rule for a mixture of 80% benzene and 20% methyl

FIG. 5.

Curves 1—4 refer to mixtures of nitrobenzene with MeOH, EtOH, *n*-PrOH and *n*-BuOH respectively.

FIG. 6.

Curves 1—3 refer to mixtures of nitrobenzene with benzene, toluene and xylene respectively.

alcohol, whereas ethyl alcohol increases it 1.66 times. Other alcohols increase it to a smaller extent. This is due to the fact that the solvent action of benzene is increased proportionately to the polarity of the alcohols. The same was found when toluene and xylene were used along with the fatty alcohols. In the case of salicylic acid also, identical results were obtained.

In all the four curves, there are maxima showing that the solubility of the acids at these points is the highest. In the case of methyl alcohol, the maximum occurs at the composition of the mixture containing 90% alcohol and 10% benzene, while in the case of ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl alcohols, the maxima occur at 80%, 70% and 70% alcohols respectively. Wagner (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, **46**, 867) and Dunstan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **85**, 817) have shown that a minimum in the viscosity-composition curve of a mixture of benzene with *n*-propyl alcohol and benzene and ethyl alcohol is obtained. They, therefore, deduce that under these circumstances, some de-association has resulted. The maxima in Fig. 4, therefore, indicate the maximum suitable polarity of the mixtures with respect to the nature of the solute.

The results of solubilities of benzoic acid in mixtures of nitrobenzene and alcohols which are plotted in Fig. 5 are very interesting. Both the components of the mixture are polar in character. The solvent action of nitrobenzene is less than that of the alcohols because the polarity of the solute is less than that of nitrobenzene. At any composition of the mixture, the solubility of the acid is greater than what is calculated from the ideal mixture rule. The nature of the curves in Fig. 5 is the same as that in Figs. 4 and 6. These results emphatically indicate that whenever a highly non-polar or highly polar solvent is used along with alcohols as one of the components of the mixture, maxima in the solubility-composition curves are always obtained. As mentioned before, this can be explained on the assumption that the more polar component of the mixture under these circumstances undergoes partial de-association.

Various predictions for the nature of solubility curves for different mixtures of solvents can also be made for different solutes. Thus the solubility curves of any solute in mixtures of aromatic hydrocarbons which are very slightly polar will be straight lines. Similarly, it is to be expected that when the constituents of a binary mixture resemble one another, as in the case of mixtures of methyl with ethyl alcohol and ethyl with propyl alcohol, the solubility should follow the mixture rule.

SUMMARY.

1. Solubilities of benzoic and salicylic acids have been determined in different binary mixtures of varying compositions.

2. The effect of mixtures of non-polar with non-polar, non-polar with polar and polar with polar solvents on the solubility of benzoic and salicylic acids has been studied.

3. It is shown that in mixtures of non-polar solvents as both the components, the solubility-composition curves are straight lines.

4. The solubility in chloroform decreases as it is diluted more and more by the addition of aromatic hydrocarbons. The solubility-composition curves are convex to the axis of composition.

5. It has been shown that the solubility in acetone decreases as it is diluted more and more by the addition of non-polar solvents such as benzene, toluene, *m*-xylene.

6. It has been shown that the solubility in alcohols first increases, reaches a maximum and then decreases as they are more and more diluted by the addition of aromatic hydrocarbons or nitrobenzene. The same is found when mixtures of nitrobenzene with different aromatic hydrocarbons are used as solvents.

7. The behaviour of salicylic acid is the same as that of benzoic acid in the same binary mixtures.

8. It has been shown that the general nature of the curves remains the same, no matter in what way the solubility or the composition of the mixture is expressed.

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